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**The Role Of Job Rotation In Preparing Educational Leaders In The Ministry Of
Education In The Kingdom Of Saudi Arabia In Light Of Transformational Leadership
Theory**

Dönüşümsel Liderlik Teorisi Işığında Suudi Arabistan Krallığı Eğitim Bakanlığı'nda Eğitim
Liderlerinin Hazırlanmasında İş Rotasyonunun Rolü

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ÖZET

Bu çalışma, dönüşümsel liderlik teorisi ışığında Suudi Arabistan Krallığı Eğitim Bakanlığı'ndaki eğitim liderlerinin yetiştirilmesinde görev rotasyonunun rolünü ölçmeyi amaçlamıştır. Suudi Arabistan Krallığı'nın Riyad kentinde gerçekleştirilen çalışmanın örnekleme, (350) çalışan ve liderden oluşmuştur. Çalışmanın sonuçları, dönüşümsel liderlik teorisi ışığında Suudi Arabistan Eğitim Bakanlığı liderleri ve çalışanlarının bakış açısına göre iş rotasyonunun eğitim liderlerinin hazırlanmasındaki rolünün orta derecede olduğunu göstermiştir. Ayrıca, yetkilendirme hariç tüm alanlarda cinsiyet etkisinden kaynaklanan istatistiksel olarak anlamlı bir fark bulunmamıştır ($\alpha = 0,05$) ve farklar kadınlar lehine olmuştur; motivasyon ve ilham hariç tüm alanlarda deneyim etkisinden kaynaklanan farklar bulunmuştur ve farklar 10 ila 20 yıldan az ve 20 yıl ve üzeri deneyim sahipleri lehine olmuştur; ve tüm alanlarda iş unvanının etkisine bağlı farklılıklar görülmüştür; bu farklılıklar kamu yönetimi müdürünün lehine olmuştur.

Anahtar Kelimeler: İş Rotasyonu, Dönüşümsel Liderlik, Liderlerin Hazırlanması.

ABSTRACT

The study aimed to measure the role of job rotation in preparing educational leaders in the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in light of the transformational leadership theory. In the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in Riyadh, the sample consisted of (350) employees and leaders. The results of the study showed that the role of job rotation in preparing educational leaders from the point of view of leaders and employees of the Ministry of Education in Saudi Arabia in light of the transformational leadership theory came to a medium degree. And there were no statistically significant differences ($\alpha = 05.0$) due to the effect of gender in all fields except for empowerment, and the differences came in favor of females, and there were differences due to the effect of experience in all fields except for motivation and inspiration, and the differences came in favor of each of 10 to less than 20 years and 20 years And more than on the other hand, and there were differences due to the effect of the job title in all fields, and the differences came in favor of the director of public administration.

Keywords: Job Rotation, Transformational Leadership, Preparation Of Leaders.

1. introduction

The world today is characterized by continuous development, dynamism, and constant change in all aspects of life. Science is evolving, and the volume of knowledge within it is increasing at rapid and successive rates. The same applies to technology and communications. This development is reflected in organizations, their objectives, structures, and activities, creating challenges that must be addressed. Therefore, organizations and governmental institutions, especially in the educational field, given its vastness, vitality, and constant evolution, must improve the skills of their individuals, enhance their capabilities, and raise their performance levels to meet established performance standards. Furthermore, individuals must be prepared for future roles and equipped to face all technological and informational changes.

Job rotation is a new and effective method for expanding managerial knowledge about the organization. It can be done vertically, by promoting managers to higher administrative positions, or horizontally, according to a specific plan aimed at increasing the experience of managers and department heads by providing them with information about all the work and activities within the organization. In addition, this method plays a role in reducing routine and boredom and fostering new ideas among managers.¹

Educational leadership is no longer limited to routine tasks; it now encompasses both administrative and technical aspects, addressing all matters related to administration, students, teachers, administrators, curricula, educational activities, technical supervision, and connecting the school with the local community.²

Transformational leadership is a fundamental factor in the development and advancement of institutions. This is due to its role in ensuring the institution's continuity and its use of various methods such as inspirational motivation, individual recognition, and intellectual stimulation. Furthermore, it has the capacity to create a suitable foundation for development and progress.³ Therefore, this study aims to measure the role of job rotation in achieving organizational change, empowering employees, and preparing future leaders in light of the dimensions and objectives of transformational leadership.

¹ Maslahah bint Hussein al-Bariqi, "Job Rotation and Its Relationship to Organizational Loyalty among Employees of the Education Department in Al-Lith", *Journal of Economic, Administrative and Legal Sciences* 1/2 (2018), 1–28.

² Wafaa al-Fawaz, "Administrative Creativity: An Approach to Developing the Performance of Female Principals of Primary Schools in Al-Kharj", *Journal of the Faculty of Education, Assiut University* 34/4 (2018), 678–700.

³ Abdullah Atiyah al-Zahrani, "Transformational Leadership and Its Impact on the Adaptive Performance of Employees: A Field Study on Saudi Insurance Sector Companies", *Arab Journal of Administrative Sciences* 23/3 (2016), 1–23.

- First Axis: Job Rotation

Like other elements in life, human beings need movement, change, and development to enhance their knowledge and experience. This can be achieved through the application of certain administrative methods, most notably job rotation. It is considered a good practice for planning, reducing boredom, and exploring employees' hidden potential. Job rotation helps management discover employees' strengths and talents and determine the most suitable roles for them. It also reveals the individual differences among employees.⁴

Job rotation is defined as: transferring individuals from one job to another to achieve several objectives, the most important of which are: improving performance, strengthening administrative leadership, and promoting the principle of reliance and competition to encourage successful and qualified administrative staff.⁵

Abdul Jalil⁶ defines job rotation as: “Transferring individuals from one job to another based on well-considered criteria to raise their efficiency and capabilities. It occurs several times, and its primary purpose is to train and develop the individual.” Job rotation aims to familiarize employees with the systems, instructions, and regulations specific to their work within the administration. It also contributes to strengthening social relationships among employees through continuous movement. Furthermore, job rotation helps combat administrative corruption in both governmental and private institutions by preventing the stagnation of officials in their positions. It also leads to improved performance, increased efficiency, and higher productivity. Job rotation is considered a fundamental pillar for developing work and increasing its effectiveness.⁷

Many thinkers and professors of management have stated that implementing job rotation leads to increased reliance on the principle of competition, encouraging successful administrative competencies. It helps employees and institutions overcome stagnation and resist changes stemming from the belief that a job belongs to the employee. It facilitates the acquisition and distribution of diverse skills and experiences across different roles. It motivates employees to

⁴ Akram Aliwa – Hamida Belkacem, “Job Rotation and Its Impact on Employee Performance” (Yüksek Lisans Tezi, University Center Abdelhafid Boussouf, Mila, Cezayir, 2020).

⁵ Ahmed Maher, *Human Resource Management* (Cairo: University Press for Printing, Publishing and Distribution, 2015).

⁶ Rabah Ramzi Abduljalil, “A Proposed Framework for Improving Performance in University Education in Light of the Job Rotation Approach: An Analytical Study”, *Journal of Educational Sciences* 2/1 (2019), 361–405.

⁷ Nasser bin Fahd al-Mudara, “Job Rotation and Its Relationship to Employees: A Survey Study on Employees of the General Administration of Administrative and Financial Affairs at the Ministry of Interior in Riyadh” (Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Naif Arab University for Security Sciences, Suudi Arabistan, 2014).

unleash their creative potential by applying the experiences and skills they have gained from one job to another. Finally, it reduces boredom and depression.⁸

According to studies by Tuei⁹ & Saina (2015) and Sanali¹⁰(2013), the most prominent advantages of job rotation include its positive impact on employee morale, providing opportunities for future promotions, and paving the way for employees to develop themselves and enhance their job performance, thus ensuring they achieve their aspirations and goals. Furthermore, it fosters perseverance, passion, and diligence, and elevates employees' professional standing. Acquiring distinctive skills, experience, knowledge, and abilities makes an employee a valuable asset, making them indispensable. Additionally, it helps organizations identify strengths, weaknesses, and gaps that could negatively affect workflow and procedures. Employee movement between jobs allows for the rapid identification of these areas, enabling the development of appropriate solutions to mitigate them as quickly as possible and address any unforeseen gaps without disrupting organizational and functional performance.

Despite the numerous advantages and benefits of job rotation, this method has drawbacks that become apparent if trainees or department heads are suddenly placed in a department without prior preparation. This will be an unpleasant experience for them and other employees. According to Flatt's study (2011), one of the most prominent disadvantages of job rotation is that it becomes negative if employees have a psychological attachment to their current job, as this may threaten their job stability, reduce performance levels and productivity, and undermine their commitment and loyalty to the organization. Job rotation may also become negative if employees are not prepared for it beforehand, as this may lead to a higher error rate due to their need for sufficient time to understand the new duties and tasks of the job, in addition to the sometimes high costs of addressing their mistakes, which leads to a decrease in the efficiency and effectiveness of the organization.

⁸ Shams Bouzidi, "The Role of Job Rotation in Empowering Employees" (Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Mohamed Boudiaf University, M'sila, Cezayir, 2017).

⁹ C. Tuei, "Job Rotation: An Examination of Its Effect on Employee Performance at KCB Branches in the North Rift Region, Kenya", *International Journal of Advanced Research in Management and Social Sciences* 2/3 (2015).

¹⁰ S. Sanali, "Job Rotation Practices, Stress and Motivation: An Empirical Study among Administrative and Diplomatic Officers in Sabah, Malaysia", *International Journal of Research in Management and Technology* 3/6 (2013), 160–166.

Al-Mudara¹¹, (2014) argues that job rotation becomes detrimental when implemented for personal gain, or when favoritism, nepotism, and cronyism influence the process of transferring or retaining employees in their positions for extended periods. It also becomes detrimental when implemented unscientifically and without prior planning. Developing specialized human resources requires considerable time and stability, and frequent employee transfers exacerbate this process unless the organization develops a sound plan to avoid such issues. This plan should include selecting the appropriate type of job rotation for each employee based on the organization's needs and objectives. Furthermore, job rotation becomes detrimental when it excludes creative and competent employees, discouraging them from achieving their ambitions and desires, and failing to utilize their qualifications, energy, and experience, which could contribute to the development and growth of both the organization and its employees.

- Third Axis: Transformational Leadership

Leadership styles employed by educational leaders have varied. Traditional leadership relies on centralization to accomplish tasks and make decisions, while modern leadership relies on diplomacy to guide the energies of employees, the local community, and students in a way that contributes to change and development. This is achieved by positively influencing employees within educational institutions. Consequently, several modern administrative theories have emerged that focus on bringing about the desired change, and among the most important of these is transformational leadership.¹²

The concept of transformational leadership is relatively recent in administrative thought. However, it has become a prominent leadership style in administrative literature and receives considerable attention from researchers. There are diverse perspectives on defining transformational leadership, and educators and researchers have not agreed on a single definition. This is due to differing viewpoints and philosophies surrounding transformational leadership, which is considered a modern concept in educational administration (Othman¹³, 2016). This has resulted in several definitions, including:

¹¹ Nasser bin Fahd al-Mudara, "Job Rotation and Its Relationship to Employees: A Survey Study on Employees of the General Administration of Administrative and Financial Affairs at the Ministry of Interior in Riyadh" (Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Naif Arab University for Security Sciences, Suudi Arabistan, 2014).

¹² Sheikha al-Askar, "Transformational and Transactional Leadership among Middle School Principals from the Perspective of Supervisors in the Educational Supervision Offices of the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia", *Journal of Educational Sciences* 22/4 (2014), 75–111.

¹³ Rania Othman, "Transformational Leadership: An Approach to Supporting the Components of a Child-Friendly School in Basic Education in Egypt", *Journal of Modern Education* 8/29 (2016), 188–193.

Transformational leadership is defined as: “The practice of involving educational leaders and their employees in decision-making, focusing on shared values to improve and develop performance, and utilizing shared visions, values, and motivation to elevate thinking to the highest levels to achieve common goals.”¹⁴

Al-Saud¹⁵ defined it as: A leadership style based on the leader's ability to create an atmosphere of friendliness, acceptance, and motivation among subordinates in the organization towards their work and the organization itself, and to foster commitment to its organizational goals and strive for its development through shared belief and complete conviction in the best interests of the work.

The researchers define it as: The ability of educational leaders to elevate the level of their followers to the best possible level in the shortest time, with the least effort and cost, focusing on preparing future leaders, while emphasizing the development of a clear future vision that supports the institution's future position, and setting realistic and clear goals for the institution.

The essential elements that define transformational leadership are as follows:

1. Ideal Influence and Charisma: This refers to the influence of a leader who possesses exceptional abilities and skills in influencing subordinates and becoming a role model. Such a leader embodies exemplary and ideal roles for their followers, who demonstrate a desire to lead in new ways to change the familiar. They also show consistency in their actions and adherence to their principles. These followers can be relied upon to do the right thing and demonstrate high levels of ethical behavior. The concept of ideal influence is fundamentally based on charismatic leadership behavior, which researchers consider to be transformational behavior.¹⁶
2. Inspirational Motivation: This refers to the ability of leaders to communicate their high expectations to employees, use symbolism to focus efforts, and express important goals simply. It means achieving more through increased effort. Motivation means that the leader motivates employees by encouraging them and creating feelings of enthusiasm. It represents the degree to which the leader explains and clarifies the vision and mission to subordinates and motivates them to be more committed to the organization's goals.¹⁷

¹⁴ al-Askar, “Transformational and Transactional Leadership”, 75–111.

¹⁵ Rateb al-Saud, *Educational Leadership: Concepts and Prospects*, 2. baskı (Amman: Dar Safaa for Printing and Publishing, 2013).

¹⁶ Kamal Downey, *Educational Leadership* (Amman: Dar al-Masirah, 2013).

¹⁷ Rateb al-Saud, *Educational Leadership: Concepts and Prospects* (Amman: Dar Safaa for Printing and Publishing, 2011).

3. Intellectual Stimulation: This refers to a transformational leader generating a set of new ideas that stimulate employees to identify problems. It also encourages them to propose potential solutions creatively and supports new and innovative work models. Furthermore, it describes the situation where a leader motivates their subordinates to be creative and innovative. These leaders are the ones who develop ideas and clarify the strengths, weaknesses, threats, and opportunities facing their organizations. Intellectual stimulation is the source of intellectual stimulation and the impetus for strategic intellectual activity.¹⁸

4. Individualized consideration: This means that leaders pay attention to their subordinates, recognize their individual differences, and deal with each employee in a specific way, guiding and training them to achieve further development and growth. The transformational leader practices a management style by being present, meaning they are close to their employees so they can easily turn to them when needed. They also delegate some tasks to them to develop their capabilities and follow up on these delegated tasks to provide further support and guidance when needed, without making them feel like they are being supervised.¹⁹

5. Empowerment: Empowerment is considered one of the essential behaviors of transformational leadership, which requires abandoning the traditional leadership model that focuses on directing towards a leadership that believes in participation and consultation. The transformational leader works to empower others to help them turn their vision into reality and maintain it. Certainly, leaders who have a transformational behavior have the ability to provide their subordinates with energy and enable them to act by providing them with a vision for the future instead of relying on a method of punishment and rewards. Leaders who have a vision can create a climate of participation and create the conditions that help for empowerment through which employees can take upon themselves the authority to make decisions that work to achieve the vision.

1.2 Previous studies

The study by Gerasimova et al. (Gerasimova, Karpacheva, Kolosova, Polyakov, Fedina, and Shchuchka, 2015)²⁰ aimed to investigate the problems facing the job rotation system in the modern education system of the Russian Federation. The study employed a qualitative

¹⁸ M. Joseph, "The Relationship between Transformational Leadership and Organizational Creativity" (Doktora Tezi, University of South Africa, 2011).

¹⁹ Qasim al-Harbi, *Modern Educational Leadership* (Amman: Al-Janadriyah, 2008).

²⁰ Elena Gerasimova – Irina Karpacheva – Irina Kolosova – Dmitry Polyakov – Natalia Fedina – Tatiana Shchuchka, "Problems and Prospects of Rotation of Pedagogical Staff in the Modern System of General Education in the Russian Federation", *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences* 6/5 (2015), 179–188.

approach, and its sample included official documents issued by executive authorities in all sectors of education in the Russian Federation, as well as strategic plans for personnel within the education system during the period 2010–2015. The results indicated a future model for employee training policy that includes consistent application of technological requirements and the development of reserve knowledge through job rotation among employees in the education sector of the former Soviet Union. The study also emphasized the importance of training professionals and graduates from educational institutions in the vocational and higher education sectors using the job rotation method.

The study by Al-Shahyounin ²¹(2018) aimed to identify job rotation and its role in developing second-tier leaders. The study population consisted of 270 employees, and the descriptive-analytical method was used, employing a questionnaire as the data collection tool. Among the most important findings were: The study participants strongly agreed with the axis concerning the reality of job rotation within the Jeddah Health Affairs Directorate. They also moderately agreed with the axis concerning the opportunities available for developing second-tier leaders within the Jeddah Health Affairs Directorate, and with the axis concerning the extent to which job rotation contributes to developing second-tier leaders within the Jeddah Health Affairs Directorate. Furthermore, the study participants strongly agreed with the axis concerning the obstacles facing job rotation within the Jeddah Health Affairs Directorate.

The study by Faraj and Al-Thubaiti (2019) ²²aimed to identify the degree of job rotation and the level of administrative development among female principals of public schools in Taif. The study employed a descriptive correlational approach, and the sample consisted of 142 female school leaders. A questionnaire was used as the data collection tool. The results indicated that the degree of job rotation implementation, from the perspective of the female principals in Taif's public schools, was moderate, while the level of administrative development in these schools was high. The study also found differences in the average responses of female principals regarding the degree of job rotation based on their academic qualifications, favoring those with a bachelor's degree or higher. No significant differences were found in the average responses of female principals regarding the degree of job rotation based on years of experience or

²¹ Khalid al-Shahyounin, "Job Rotation and Its Role in Preparing Second-Tier Leaders: An Applied Study in the Directorate of Health Affairs in Jeddah Governorate" (Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Naif Arab University for Security Sciences, 2018).

²² Shatha Faraj – Asma al-Thubaiti, "Job Rotation and Its Relationship to Administrative Development among Female Principals of Public Schools in Taif", *Umm Al-Qura University Journal of Educational and Psychological Sciences* 10/2 (2019), 339–370.

academic qualifications. Finally, the study revealed a correlation between the degree of job rotation and the level of administrative development among female principals of public schools in Taif.

The study also found a correlation between the degree of job rotation and the level of administrative development among female principals of public schools in Taif. Al-Zamil's²³ study (2020) aimed to identify the degree to which administrative leaders practice transformational leadership and its relationship to change leadership in some Saudi universities. To achieve the study's objective, a questionnaire was designed that included (20) items. The study sample consisted of (205) members of the teaching staff in some Saudi universities. The descriptive analytical method was followed. The study concluded that the degree to which administrative leaders practice transformational leadership was high, and that there were statistically significant differences between the average ratings of the study sample attributable to the university, in favor of the sample members at King Saud University in all areas. There were statistically significant differences for all axes of the overall degree of transformational leadership attributable to the variable of nature of work and experience in favor of males, and there was a statistically significant positive relationship between transformational leadership and change management.

In Al-Khudair²⁴'s 2021 study, "Developing Sustainable Leadership Performance in Public Education in Light of the Dutch Experience," the study aimed to identify the concept of sustainable leadership, its most important requirements, and the most prominent Dutch practices for developing sustainable leadership performance in public education. The descriptive survey method was used, and through an analysis of the literature and previous studies, the study reached several conclusions, the most important of which are: that sustainable leadership is capable of meeting the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Furthermore, among the most important requirements of sustainable leadership are the integration of all elements of the educational institution in a comprehensive improvement process; maintaining successful outcomes; supporting and empowering staff as professional leaders; the ability to predict and solve complex problems; managing emotions; formulating and sharing a vision; preparing a strategic

²³ Maha Othman al-Zamil, "The Degree of Administrative Leaders' Practice of Transformational Leadership and Its Relationship to Leading Change in Some Saudi Universities", *Journal of the Islamic University for Educational and Psychological Studies* 28/6 (2020).

²⁴ Hadeel Suleiman al-Khudair, "Developing Sustainable Leadership Performance in Public Education in Light of the Dutch Experience", *Journal of Arts, Literature, Humanities and Social Sciences* 69 (2021), 97–112.

plan with a long-term perspective; regularly evaluating sustainable practices; flexibility; managing change; continuous professional development; material and moral incentives; encouraging creative and innovative ideas; social and environmental responsibility; decision-making with stakeholders; building external partnerships; successful leadership succession planning; ethical integrity; and practicing ethical and transformational leadership.

Al-Harbi²⁵'s study (2021) aimed to identify the extent to which secondary school leaders practice transformational leadership and its relationship to organizational commitment from the perspective of male and female teachers in Makkah. The descriptive-analytical method was employed, and the study sample consisted of 500 male and female teachers from secondary schools in Makkah. The results concluded that there was statistical significance at the significance level for the extent to which secondary school leaders practice transformational leadership and its relationship to organizational commitment from the perspective of male and female teachers in Makkah.

A review of previous Arab and international studies on job rotation and transformational leadership reveals numerous and varied findings that highlight the importance and role of job rotation and transformational leadership in achieving organizational stability and success, and increasing the productivity of its members.

This study differs and is distinguished by its attempt to measure the role of job rotation in preparing educational leaders in the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, in light of transformational leadership theory. To keep pace with contemporary technological and knowledge developments and challenges, and to improve the educational process and enhance its outputs to the required level, this study will also contribute to enriching the scientific and applied aspect of the subject of study.

1.3 The problem addressed in the study and its questions:

Undoubtedly, employees and administrators are susceptible to burnout and thus fall victim to inflexible work styles and systems. The organization they work for also suffers, as performance within that organization will be low, or even nonexistent, impacting the overall productivity of the administrative apparatus. Several studies, such as those by Faraj and Al-Thubaiti (2019), have pointed to deficiencies in the preparation of educational leaders and emphasized the importance of adopting job rotation in leadership development across all institutions, including educational ones. The job rotation that this study aims to implement involves moving

²⁵ al-Harbi, *Modern Educational Leadership*.

employees from their current position to another, either horizontally or vertically, with the goal of equipping them with technical, behavioral, interpersonal, and leadership skills, as well as diverse experiences, thereby preparing and developing future leaders.

Despite the role played by the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in training and preparing educational leaders to keep pace with the changing times and developments in the educational field, employees may remain in their positions for extended periods without change or development. Some employees may even begin their careers and retire in the same department or administration without any significant change. This undermines the importance of investing in human resources efficiently and effectively, and of establishing a structured leadership succession within the Ministry. Furthermore, there is a decline in interest in implementing job rotation, particularly in the area of leadership development and training. Many leaders and employees within the Ministry of Education are unfamiliar with this approach and its objectives. Some employees resist change, and there is a pressing need to cultivate transformational educational leaders capable of propelling the Ministry to a more advanced position, enabling it to achieve the goals of Saudi Vision 2030. All of this necessitates the reactivation of several policies and procedures related to human resource development and leadership preparation, including job rotation. Therefore, this study proposes a number of administrative requirements for activating job rotation in the preparation of educational leaders within the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, based on the theory of transformational leadership. This will be achieved by **addressing the following questions:**

1. What is the role of job rotation in preparing educational leaders in the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, in light of transformational leadership theory?
2. Are there statistically significant differences at the ($\alpha=0.05$) level in the mean responses of the study sample regarding the role of job rotation in preparing educational leaders in the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, in light of transformational leadership theory, attributable to the variables of gender, job position, and experience?

1.4 Study Objectives: The current study aims to:

1. Identify the role of job rotation in preparing educational leaders in the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, in light of transformational leadership theory.
2. Determine whether there are statistically significant differences at the ($\alpha=0.05$) level in the mean responses of the study sample regarding the role of job rotation in preparing educational leaders in the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, in light of

transformational leadership theory, attributable to the variables of gender, job position, and experience.

1.5 The Importance of the Study: The importance of this study can be illustrated through the following:

- Theoretical Importance:

1. The topic of preparing educational leaders is crucial and has implications for educational life and its outcomes.
2. The problem of relying on traditional methods in preparing educational leaders has negative effects on the educational process in general, and on its outcomes in particular.

- Practical Importance:

1. This study can benefit officials in the training and human resources sectors of the Ministry of Education in their efforts to overcome stagnation and adopt modern methods in preparing educational leaders.
2. This study can contribute to changing the educational climate within the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, ensuring the smooth operation of the educational process and the quality of its outcomes. This can be achieved by fostering a shared understanding among leaders and staff within the Ministry regarding the goals and tasks of each department, thereby achieving greater coordination between these tasks and goals, which ultimately benefits the educational process.
3. The study can contribute to changing educational policies for preparing leaders in a way that achieves the goals and ambitions of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030.

1.6 Study Terminology: Based on the study variables, the researcher provided the following definitions:

Job Rotation: This was defined as the rotation of positions within the workplace and a new method for expanding managerial knowledge about the organization. It can be vertical, involving the promotion of managers to higher administrative positions, or horizontal, through transfers to positions at the same level, with the aim of increasing managerial experience and acquiring knowledge and information about the operations and units within the organization (Abduljalil 2019: 361).

Operationally, it is defined as the score obtained from the responses of the study sample on the scale developed by the researchers.

Transformational leadership: This is leadership that expands and activates the interests of subordinates, deepens their understanding and acceptance of the group's vision and goals, and

broadens their perspective to consider beyond their own self-interest for the greater good of the organization (Al-Zahrani, 2016:5). Operationally, it is defined as the score obtained from the responses of the study participants on the scale developed by the researchers..

Leadership development: This is defined as the process of preparing individuals for positions that align with their abilities and specializations through training and promotion to leadership roles. This is done according to a program planned for the entire workforce by senior management to meet the organization's future staffing needs and the needs of individuals for career advancement within the organization (Jumah, 2018:141).

1.7 Study Scope: The researcher conducted this study within the following parameters:

- **Human Scope:** The study sample was limited to a number of employees and leaders at all levels and job positions working at the Ministry of Education headquarters in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.
- **Temporal Scope:** The study was conducted during the 2020/2021 academic year.
- **Geographical Scope:** The study was conducted at the Ministry of Education headquarters in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.

1.8 Study Methodology: The descriptive analytical method was used as it was suitable for the purposes of the study.

- **Study Population and Sample:** The study population consisted of all employees and leaders working at the headquarters of the Ministry of Education in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, totaling (4000) employees and leaders (Human Resources Department, Ministry of Education, 2020). A representative sample of (350) employees and leaders was selected using stratified random sampling. Table (1) shows the distribution of the study sample according to its variables.

Table (1): Frequencies and percentages according to study variables

Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	197	56.3%
Female	153	43.7%
Experience		
Less than 10 years	147	42.0%
10 to less than 20 years	88	25.1%
20 years and above	115	32.9%
Job Title		
Leader (Managers and Department Heads)	128	36.6%
Employee	222	63.4%

Total	350	100.0%
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Study Instrument: A questionnaire consisting of (61) items distributed across five domains (attractiveness and influence, individual considerations, motivation and inspiration, empowerment, and intellectual stimulation) was developed to measure the role of job rotation in preparing educational leaders in the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, in light of transformational leadership theory, from the perspective of leaders and employees within the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

Instrument Validity: The content validity of the questionnaire was verified by presenting it to a group of (10) expert reviewers specializing in educational leadership and its principles at Jordanian and Saudi universities. The reviewers provided their opinions on the accuracy and validity of the questionnaire's content in terms of item clarity, linguistic formulation, suitability for measuring its intended purpose, and its relevance to the relevant domain. They also suggested adding, modifying, or deleting any items they deemed appropriate. All items were approved without modification.

The correlation coefficients of each item were extracted with the total score, with each item and its correlation with the domain to which it belongs, and with the domains with each other and the total score, in a pilot sample from outside the study sample consisting of (30) educational leaders. The correlation coefficients of the items with the instrument as a whole ranged between (0.94-73.0), and with the domain (94.0-79.0). Table (2) shows this:

Table (2): Correlation coefficients between the item, the total score, and the domain to which it belongs

Paragraph Number	With Field	With Tool	Paragraph Number	With Field	With Tool	Paragraph Number	With Field	With Tool
1	.91**	.83**	22	.91**	.85**	43	.88**	.89**
2	.84**	.87**	23	.86**	.83**	44	.91**	.87**
3	.91**	.85**	24	.81**	.79**	45	.91**	.88**
4	.88**	.78**	25	.89**	.82**	46	.90**	.89**
5	.88**	.85**	26	.88**	.89**	47	.89**	.87**
6	.84**	.75**	27	.89**	.83**	48	.84**	.84**
7	.83**	.81**	28	.80**	.80**	49	.93**	.89**
8	.93**	.84**	29	.88**	.83**	50	.85**	.85**
9	.93**	.85**	30	.94**	.91**	51	.92**	.91**

10	.83**	.74**	31	.93**	.92**	52	.93**	.92**
11	.88**	.89**	32	.92**	.83**	53	.92**	.90**
12	.85**	.79**	33	.88**	.88**	54	.89**	.87**
13	.83**	.80**	34	.93**	.89**	55	.93**	.87**
14	.87**	.84**	35	.92**	.88**	56	.94**	.88**
15	.86**	.86**	36	.94**	.94**	57	.89**	.85**
16	.86**	.88**	37	.93**	.92**	58	.85**	.81**
17	.84**	.84**	38	.87**	.85**	59	.83**	.77**
18	.79**	.73**	39	.90**	.87**	60	.89**	.82**
19	.86**	.82**	40	.90**	.88**	61	.87**	.80**
20	.89**	.82**	41	.87**	.89**			
21	.91**	.89**	42	.94**	.93**			

***Statistically significant at the significance level (0.05) **Statistically significant at the significance level (0.1).**

Reliability of the study instrument: To ensure the reliability of the study instrument, the reliability coefficient was calculated using the internal consistency method according to Cronbach's alpha equation, by applying the scale to a group outside the study sample consisting of (30). Table No. (3) shows the internal consistency coefficient according to Cronbach's alpha equation for the domains and the total score, and these values were considered suitable for the purposes of this study.

Table (3): Cronbach's alpha internal consistency coefficient and test-retest reliability for domains and total score

Domain	Internal Consistency
Attractiveness and Impact	0.92
Motivation and Inspiration	0.93
Intellectual Stimulation	0.88
Individual Considerations	0.94
Empowerment	0.93

1.9. Study Results:

First Question: What is the role of job rotation in preparing educational leaders in the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, in light of transformational leadership theory?

To answer this question, the arithmetic means and standard deviations for the role of job rotation in preparing educational leaders in the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, in light of transformational leadership theory, were calculated. Table (4) illustrates this.

Table (4): Arithmetic means and standard deviations for the role of job rotation in preparing educational leaders in the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, in light of transformational leadership theory, arranged in descending order of arithmetic means.

Rank	Number	Domain	Mean	Standard Deviation	Degree
1	1	Attractiveness and Impact	3.32	1.037	Average
2	4	Individual Considerations	3.30	1.145	Average
3	2	Motivation and Inspiration	3.29	1.072	Average
4	5	Empowerment	3.29	1.172	Average
5	3	Intellectual Stimulation	3.28	1.167	Average
		Overall Scale	3.29	1.073	Average

Table (4) shows that the arithmetic means ranged between (28.3 - 32.3), all at a moderate level. Attractiveness and influence ranked first with the highest arithmetic mean of (32.3), while intellectual stimulation ranked last with an arithmetic mean of (28.3). The arithmetic mean for the role of job rotation in preparing educational leaders in the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, in light of the transformational leadership theory as a whole, was (29.3) with a standard deviation of (1.073).

The researchers explain this result by pointing to the weak adoption of job rotation by the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom as one of the important methods for preparing, training and developing leaders. The Ministry relies heavily in this regard on training programs such as lectures and seminars, such as the Leaders Preparation Program and the Future Leaders Platform, which the Ministry launched during the past period. In addition, there is a deficiency in implementing job rotation within the Ministry in the desired manner, and it is limited to transfers of the administrative staff, whether within the Ministry or the educational districts. Consequently, most employees do not have knowledge or familiarity with job rotation. Moreover, the systems, procedures and financial incentives followed in the Ministry may be an obstacle to implementing job rotation to a more comprehensive degree within the Ministry. In addition, there is a lack of promotion of the culture of job rotation within the Ministry, and a weak awareness of the importance of job rotation and what it achieves in terms of developing human resources in general and leaders in particular. This creates a kind of resistance to implementing this method and resistance to any change in work methods or job positions. The

result of the current study differed from the result of Al-Shahyounin’s study (2018), which revealed that the study sample agreed to a high degree on the reality of job rotation in the Health Affairs Directorate in Jeddah Governorate.

Question 2: Are there statistically significant differences at the ($\alpha=0.05$) level in the role of job rotation in preparing educational leaders in the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, based on transformational leadership theory, attributable to the variables of gender, experience, and job title?

To answer this question, the means and standard deviations for the role of job rotation in preparing educational leaders in the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, based on transformational leadership theory, were calculated according to the variables of gender, experience, and job title. Table (5) illustrates this.

Table (5): Means and Standard Deviations for the Role of Job Rotation in Preparing Educational Leaders in the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, Based on Transformational Leadership Theory, Attributable to the Variables of Gender, Experience, and Job Title

	Attractiveness and Impact	Motivation and Inspiration	Intellectual Stimulation	Individual Considerations	Empowerment	Overall
Gender						
Male	Mean (S)	0.81	0.76	0.79	0.81	0.78
	Standard Deviation (SD)	1.26	1.21	1.30	1.31	1.28
Female	Mean (S)	0.77	0.83	0.87	0.88	0.89
	Standard Deviation (SD)	1.07	1.11	1.19	1.17	1.06
Experience						
Less than 10 years	Mean (S)	0.54	0.56	0.67	0.57	0.59
	Standard Deviation (SD)	1.04	1.07	1.17	1.10	1.08
10 to less than 20 years	Mean (S)	1.00	0.97	0.93	1.05	0.99
	Standard Deviation (SD)	1.26	1.22	1.32	1.41	1.32

20 years and above	Mean (S)	0.95	0.94	0.94	1.02	1.01
	Standard Deviation (SD)	1.24	1.20	1.29	1.25	1.17
Job Title						
General Manager	Mean (S)	1.04	1.02	1.04	1.10	1.09
	Standard Deviation (SD)	1.37	1.29	1.34	1.39	1.35
Employee	Mean (S)	0.64	0.66	0.70	0.69	0.67
	Standard Deviation (SD)	1.02	1.06	1.18	1.14	1.05

x = arithmetic mean y = standard deviation

Table (5) shows an apparent variance in the arithmetic means and standard deviations regarding the role of job rotation in preparing educational leaders at the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, based on transformational leadership theory, due to differences in the categories of gender, experience, and job title variables.

To determine the statistical significance of the differences between the arithmetic means, a three-way multivariate analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used across all domains, as shown in Table (6).

Table (6): Three-way multivariate analysis of variance of the effect of gender, experience, and job title on the domains of the role of job rotation in preparing educational leaders at the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, based on transformational leadership theory.

Source of Variance	Domains	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Squares	F-value	Statistical Significance	Effect Size
Gender	Attractiveness and Impact	1.292	1	1.292	0.968	0.326	0.003
	Motivation and Inspiration	4.547	1	4.547	3.486	0.063	0.010
	Intellectual Stimulation	4.364	1	4.364	2.842	0.093	0.008
	Individual Considerations	5.390	1	5.390	3.613	0.058	0.010
	Empowerment	7.326	1	7.326	5.469	0.020	0.016

Experience	Overall	9.546	2	4.773	3.575	0.029	0.020
	Attractiveness and Impact	8.415	2	4.207	3.226	0.041	0.018
	Motivation and Inspiration	3.476	2	1.738	1.132	0.324	0.007
	Intellectual Stimulation	11.576	2	5.788	3.880	0.022	0.022
	Individual Considerations	9.141	2	4.570	3.412	0.034	0.019
Job Title	Empowerment	7.335	1	7.335	5.494	0.020	0.016
	Overall	7.707	1	7.707	5.910	0.016	0.017
	Attractiveness and Impact	8.275	1	8.275	5.390	0.021	0.015
	Motivation and Inspiration	9.857	1	9.857	6.608	0.011	0.019
	Intellectual Stimulation	12.016	1	12.016	8.970	0.003	0.025
Error	Individual Considerations	460.619	345	1.335			
	Empowerment	449.957	345	1.304			
	Overall	529.696	345	1.535			
	Attractiveness and Impact	514.639	345	1.492			
	Motivation and Inspiration	462.142	345	1.340			
Total	Intellectual Stimulation	483.940	349				
	Individual Considerations	472.537	349				
	Empowerment	545.793	349				
	Overall	544.417	349				

Table (6) shows the following:

- There are no statistically significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$) attributable to gender, with an F-value of 3.355 and a statistical significance of 0.068. This could be attributed to the gender variable, as most educational leaders and ministry employees, both male and female, are qualified and knowledgeable about modern leadership methods. This is further supported by

gender equality, women's empowerment, and their assumption of leadership positions within the ministry. Both genders share a strong desire to achieve the desired development and cultivate effective leaders capable of fulfilling the goals of both employees and the ministry. The researcher explains the differences in empowerment, which favor females, by suggesting that females are more enthusiastic about the concept of empowerment and more eager to assume leadership positions, similar to the males who have historically held a dominant position in leadership roles over the past decades.

- There were statistically significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$) attributed to the effect of job title, with an F-value of 6.941 and a statistical significance of 0.09. These differences favored general managers. The researcher interprets this result as indicating that general managers are more aware than employees of the importance of implementing job rotation based on transformational leadership theory, due to the nature of their administrative work. It is also evident that general managers understand the positive outcomes of transformational leadership and the importance and benefits of job rotation in developing and enhancing human resources in general, and educational leaders in particular, which ultimately benefits the ministry and helps it achieve its goals with efficiency and effectiveness.

- There were statistically significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$) attributed to the effect of experience, with an F-value of 3.235 and a statistical significance of 0.041. To determine the statistically significant pairwise differences between the arithmetic means, post-hoc comparisons were used, as shown in Table (7).

Table (7): Scheffé's post-hoc comparisons of the impact of experience on the role of job rotation in preparing educational leaders in the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in light of transformational leadership theory

Domains	Categories	Mean	Less than 10 years	10 to less than 20 years	20 years and above
Attractiveness and Impact	Less than 10 years	0.54			
	10 to less than 20 years	1.00	0.46*		
	20 years and above	0.95	0.41*	0.048	
Intellectual Stimulation	Less than 10 years	0.56			
	10 to less than 20 years	0.97	0.41*		

	20 years and above	0.94	0.38*	0.030	
Individual Considerations	Less than 10 years	0.57			
	10 to less than 20 years	1.05	0.47*		
	20 years and above	1.02	0.44*	0.02	
Empowerment	Less than 10 years	0.59			
	10 to less than 20 years	0.99	0.40*		
	20 years and above	1.01	0.42*	0.02	
Overall Grade	Less than 10 years	0.58			
	10 to less than 20 years	0.99	0.41*		
	20 years and above	0.97	0.39*	0.016	

Significant at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Table (7) shows statistically significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$) between those with less than 10 years of experience and those with 10 to less than 20 years of experience, and those with 20 years of experience and above. These differences favored those with 10 to less than 20 years of experience and those with 20 years of experience and above. The researcher interprets this result as indicating that educational leaders have a deeper understanding of their work and a higher degree of professional maturity. They are also more aware of the importance of professional development and the practice of modern leadership styles. What was practiced in the past may not be successful in the present.

1.10 Recommendations:

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher recommends the following:

- 1-** The necessity of implementing job rotation to prepare educational leaders within the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, based on the theory of transformational leadership.
- 2-** The necessity of continuously focusing on preparing, qualifying, and developing educational leaders within the Ministry of Education to ensure a constant supply of qualified and influential leaders to leadership positions within the Ministry, enabling it to achieve its objectives.
- 3-** The importance of including job rotation within the training policies implemented by the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, as well as within leadership succession plans.

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Etik Beyan / Ethical Statement

Bu çalışmanın hazırlanma sürecinde bilimsel ve etik ilkelere uyulduğu ve yararlanılan tüm çalışmaların kaynakçada belirtildiği beyan olunur.
It is declared that scientific and ethical principles have been followed while carrying out and writing this study and that all the sources used have been properly cited.

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The author declares that he have no competing interests.

Yazar Katkıları / Authors Contributions:

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